

Comparing Toxicities between 18 Gy in 2 Fractions vs 21 Gy in 3 Fractions of Brachytherapy after Concurrent Chemoradiotherapy in Locally Advanced Carcinoma Cervix

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Abstract

Background: Cervical cancer remains a major global health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where late-stage diagnosis is a common phenomenon. For patients with locally advanced cervical carcinoma (LACC), concurrent chemoradiotherapy (CCRT) followed by high-dose-rate (HDR) brachytherapy is the standard treatment modality.

Aim: This study aimed to compare early toxicity outcomes of two HDR brachytherapy regimens—18 Gy in 2 fractions versus 21 Gy in 3 fractions—administered after CCRT in patients with LACC.

Methods: A quasi-experimental study was conducted at the National Institute of Cancer Research and Hospital (NICRH), Dhaka, between July 2023 and December 2024. A total of 66 histopathologically confirmed LACC patients were enrolled and divided equally into two arms: Arm A: 18 Gy in 2 fractions and Arm B: 21 Gy in 3 fractions.

All patients received external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) at 50 Gy in 25 fractions over 5 weeks with concurrent weekly cisplatin (40 mg/m²), followed by HDR brachytherapy per their assigned arm. Early toxicities were assessed at 6-, 12- and 24-weeks post-treatment using CTCAE v5.0. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 27, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Findings: Most patients were aged 30–50 years and from low socio-economic backgrounds, contributing to delayed diagnosis. Acute toxicity profiles were largely comparable between the two arms. At 12 weeks, anemia was absent in 96.9% of Arm A and 100% of Arm B; at 6 weeks, Grade II proctitis was reported in 9.1% (Arm A) and 6.0% (Arm B); at 12 weeks, skin toxicity occurred in 6.1% of patients in both arms and at 24 weeks, Grade I vaginal dryness was noted in 9.1% (Arm A) and 12.1% (Arm B). No statistically significant differences were found in hematological, gastrointestinal, genitourinary, dermatological, or vaginal toxicities between the two regimens.

Conclusion: The 18 Gy in 2 fractions HDR brachytherapy regimen demonstrated comparable early toxicity outcomes to the 21 Gy in 3 fractions schedule, with the added advantage of shorter treatment duration. This makes it a viable, resource-efficient option for managing LACC in low-resource settings. Further large-scale studies with long-term follow-up are warranted to assess late toxicities, loco-regional control, and survival outcomes.

More Information

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Keywords:

Locally advanced cervical cancer, Toxicity, concurrent chemoradiotherapy, brachytherapy, carcinoma cervix, malignancy.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer remains a major global health challenge, ranking as the fourth most commonly diagnosed cancer and the fourth leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women worldwide, according to GLOBOCAN 2018 [1]. In early-stage disease, either surgery or radiotherapy as a single modality can yield favorable outcomes. However, in cases of locally advanced cervical carcinoma (LACC), a combined modality approach — concurrent chemoradiotherapy (CCRT) — is considered the standard of care [2].

Despite advances in treatment, nearly half of the LACC cases still experience failure in the locoregional area [2]. This failure is often due to the large tumor volume, increased hypoxic cell populations, compromised tumor geometry, impaired vascular supply and elevated cellular proliferation—all of which tend to reduce radiation sensitivity [3]. To impede these obstacles, the standard regimen includes external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) and intracavitary radiotherapy (ICRT), followed by brachytherapy, whenever feasible [4].

Brachytherapy enables direct delivery of high-dose radiation to the tumor, minimizing exposure to surrounding healthy tissues [14]. High-dose-rate (HDR) brachytherapy has become the global standard, offering advantages such as reduced overall treatment duration and improved local tumor control [5]. The primary objective of brachytherapy is to deliver an adequate dose to the cervix and surrounding paracervical tissues while sparing critical adjacent organs, such as the uterus and vaginal vault, which are relatively radioresistant [6].

Multiple studies have explored different HDR brachytherapy fractionation schedules—most commonly 2 or 3 fractions—with evidence suggesting comparable complication rates and no significant increase in toxicity, even with fewer fractions [7]. For instance, Patel and friends evaluated 121 patients with stage I–III cervical cancer treated with EBRT (40–46 Gy) followed by two 9 Gy fractions of HDR brachytherapy. Over a 3–7-year follow-up period, the study reported a 5-year local control rate of 74.5% and a grade 3 or higher toxicity rate of only 3.31% [7].

Bangladesh is a low-resource country. Trimming the overall treatment time, limiting the extent of tumor repopulation and increasing the probability of tumor control for a given total dose would be some factors underlying the use of 18 Gy 2 fractions of brachytherapy instead of 21 Gy 3 fractions. Shorter treatment time leads to lesser hospital stays which will eventually enhance the feasibility to patients. This investigation was conducted to observe and compare the toxicity outcomes following the treatment of LACC

with two fractions of HDR brachytherapy following conventional concurrent chemoradiation.

Materials and Methods

Study design, participants and settings

This quasi-experimental study was performed in the Department of Radiation Oncology, National Institute of Cancer Research & Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The duration of the study was July, 2023 to December, 2024 (18 months).

Patients of locally advanced stage (Stage IIB-IVA) carcinoma cervix were enrolled in this research by means of purposive sampling technique. The total number of participants were 66; they were distributed equally into 2 arms; Arm A and Arm B.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Age ≥ 18 years.
- Clinically diagnosed and histopathologically confirmed locally advanced stage (FIGO Stage IIB to IVA) squamous cell carcinoma of uterine cervix.
- Patients with ECOG (Eastern Co-operative Oncology Group) performance status up to 2.

Exclusion criteria

- Pregnant and lactating woman.
- Serious concomitant medical condition including severe heart disease, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, hypertension or psychiatric illness.
- Patients suffering pelvic infection.
- Recurrent cases of carcinoma cervix.
- Post-operative patients of carcinoma cervix.
- Adenocarcinoma & other varieties of carcinoma cervix.

Study Procedure

Data for this study were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire. Prior to treatment initiation, all patients received detailed counseling on the treatment protocol, potential radiation-related toxicities, nutritional advice, personal care, and expected outcomes.

All enrolled patients underwent external beam radiation therapy (EBRT) combined with concurrent weekly cisplatin chemotherapy (40 mg/m²). EBRT was administered via a linear accelerator (LINAC), delivering a total dose of 50 Gy in 25 fractions (2 Gy per fraction) over a period of 5 weeks.

Following EBRT, patients received high-dose-rate (HDR) intracavitary brachytherapy according to their assigned group:

- Arm A: 18 Gy delivered in 2 fractions (9 Gy per fraction), administered weekly over 2 weeks.
- Arm B: 21 Gy delivered in 3 fractions (7 Gy per fraction), administered weekly over 3 weeks.

Thus, the total treatment duration was approximately 7 weeks for Arm A and 8 weeks for Arm B.

Patients were evaluated weekly during the course of treatment for clinical assessment and toxicity monitoring. After completion of therapy, all patients were scheduled for follow-up to assess acute toxicities, with the first follow-up visit at 6 weeks post-treatment. Subsequent follow-ups were conducted at 3-month intervals for the next 6 months to monitor treatment-related adverse effects and patient recovery.

HDR Brachytherapy

Brachytherapy is short-distance therapy. It is a form of radiotherapy where a radioactive material is inserted directly into or next to a tumor and concentrates the dose there. The ICRU report 38 defines brachytherapy dose rate and HDR (high dose rate) is 12Gy/Hour.

Assessment of Acute Toxicities

- Gastrointestinal
- Genitourinary
- Hematological
- Skin

All the toxicities were assessed using Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) V5.0 toxicity grading. [8]

Assessment of Socio-Economic Status

According to Bangladesh Economic Association (BEA): [9]

1. Lower Class: Monthly household income- <12,500 BDT
2. Middle Class: Monthly household income- 12,500-21,500 BDT
3. Upper Class: Monthly household income- >21,500 BDT.

Statistics

Following data collection, all entries were checked and verified for completeness and consistency. Data were tabulated and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 27.0.1. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the variables: frequencies and percentages were used for categorical variables, while means and standard deviations were calculated for continuous variables [15].

Comparative analysis of categorical variables between the two study arms was conducted using the Chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test, as appropriate. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant [16]. The results were presented in the form of tables and figures as relevant to illustrate key findings.

Ethics

This study received ethical clearance from the Ethical Review Committee of the National Institute of Cancer Research and Hospital (NICRH). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Patients were informed about the study objectives, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. The study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki

(1964), and its subsequent amendments concerning research involving human subjects.

Results

Table 1 highlights the socio-demographic attributes of the respondents. It is clearly visible that, majority of the participants (66.7% vs. 69.6%) belonged to the age group of 30-49 years. It can be also seen that, most of them (72.7% vs. 78.7%) were housewives. Lastly, it was found that maximum respondents (66.6% vs. 72.7%) hailed from lower class of socio-economic background.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (n=66)

Characteristics	Arm A (n=33) [n/%]	Arm B (n=33) [n/%]	p value
Age group [in years]			
19-29	5 (15.2)	5 (15.2)	0.945 ⁺
30-49	22 (66.7)	23 (69.6)	
50-70	6 (18.1)	5 (15.2)	
Occupation			
Housewife	24 (72.7)	26 (78.7)	0.846 [^]
Day laborer	5 (15.2)	4 (12.1)	
Service holder	4 (12.1)	3 (9.1)	
Socio-economic condition*			
Lower class	22 (66.6)	24 (72.7)	0.834 [^]
Middle class	9 (27.3)	8 (24.2)	
Upper class	2 (6.1)	1 (3.0)	

Note: *According to Bangladesh Economic Association 2023; ⁺p value determined by Chi Square test; [^]p value determined by Fisher’s Exact test.

Table 2: Hematological Toxicities at Different Times (n=66)

Anemia at various times	Arm A (n=33) [n/%]	Arm B (n=33) [n/%]	p-value	
Anemia just after CCRT				
Absent	31 (93.8)	32 (96.9)	1.00	
Grade I	2 (6.1)	1 (3.1)		
Anemia during 1st follow up				
Absent	32 (96.9)	33 (100.0)		
Grade 1	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)		
Anemia during 2nd follow up				
Absent	32 (96.9)	33 (100.0)		
Grade 1	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)		
Anemia during 3rd follow up				
Absent	31 (93.9)	33 (100.0)		
Grade 1	2 (6.1)	0 (0.0)		

Note: *p-value was determined by Fisher’s Exact test.

It is clearly visible that, hematological toxicity, indicated by anemia, was absent in majority of the cases. For instance, during 1st follow up, 96.9% vs. 100.0% cases had no anemia. However, prevalence of Grade 1

anemia was more in Arm A than Arm B; for example, during 3rd follow up, 6.1% vs. 0.0% Grade 1 anemia was reported. No statistically significant association was found (p=1.00). Table 2 elaborates hematological toxicities experienced by the study sample at different points of time.

Table 3: Comparing the Toxicities During the 1st Follow Up in Both the Groups (n=66)

Toxicities	Arm A (n=33) [n/%]	Arm B (n=33) [n/%]	p-value
Diarrhea			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	3 (9.1)	3 (9.1)	
Grade II	0 (0.0)	1 (3.0)	
Proctitis			
Grade 0	29 (87.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	1 (3.0)	2 (6.0)	
Grade II	3 (9.1)	2 (6.0)	
Bladder toxicity			
Dysuria			
Grade 0	28 (84.8)	27 (81.8)	1.00
Grade I	2 (6.0)	5 (15.2)	
Grade II	3 (9.2)	1 (3.0)	
Increased urinary frequency			
Grade 0	29 (87.9)	27 (81.8)	0.733
Grade I	2 (6.0)	5 (15.2)	
Grade II	2 (6.0)	1 (3.0)	
Vaginal toxicity			
Vaginitis			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	3 (9.1)	4 (12.1)	
Vaginal dryness			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	3 (9.1)	4 (12.1)	
Skin toxicity			
Grade 0	28 (84.8)	27 (81.8)	1.00
Grade I	4 (12.2)	5 (15.2)	
Grade II	1 (3.0)	1 (3.0)	

Note: *p-value estimated by Fisher’s Exact Test.

We assessed the various toxicities during the first follow up. It was clear that, majority of the participants (90.9% vs. 87.9%) did not complain of any diarrhea. Similarly, maximum patients (87.9% vs 87.9%) did not report any symptoms of proctitis. However, despite most of the respondents did not complain of any sort of bladder toxicities; Grade I dysuria and increased frequency of micturition was found more in Arm B (15.2%; 15.2%) compared to Arm A (6.0%; 6.0%) respectively. Similarly, vaginal toxicities such as vaginitis and vaginal dryness were also slightly more pronounced in case of Arm B (12.1%; 12.1%) than Arm A (9.1%; 9.1%) respectively. Lastly, skin toxicities were

mostly absent (84.8% vs. 81.8%) in Arm A & B respectively. None of the associations were found to be statistically significant. Table 3 describes the toxicities during the 1st follow up session in both the groups.

Table 4: Comparing the Toxicities During the 2nd Follow Up in Both the Groups (n=66)

Toxicities	Arm A (n=33) [n/%]	Arm B (n=33) [n/%]	p-value
Diarrhea			
Grade 0	32 (97.0)	31 (93.9)	1.00
Grade I	1 (3.0)	2 (6.1)	
Proctitis			
Grade 0	31 (93.9)	32 (97.0)	1.00
Grade I	2 (6.1)	1 (3.0)	
Bladder toxicity			
Dysuria			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	30 (90.9)	1.00
Grade I	1 (3.0)	2 (6.1)	
Grade II	2 (6.1)	1 (3.0)	
Increased urinary frequency			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	31 (94.0)	1.00
Grade I	2 (6.1)	1 (3.0)	
Grade II	1 (3.0)	1 (3.0)	
Vaginal toxicity			
Vaginal dryness			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	3 (9.1)	4 (12.1)	
Skin toxicity			
Grade 0	31 (93.9)	31 (93.9)	1.00
Grade I	2 (6.1)	2 (6.1)	

Note: *p-value estimated by Fisher’s Exact Test.

It was seen that, during the 2nd follow up, only 1 vs. 2 participants reported Grade I diarrhea. Similarly, Grade I proctitis was detected in 2 vs. 1 respondent. Moreover, majority of the patients did not complain of any bladder toxicities such as dysuria (90.9% vs. 90.9%) or increased frequency of micturition (90.9% vs. 94.0%). In addition, vaginal (90.9% vs. 87.9%) and skin (93.9% vs. 93.9%) toxicities were also absent in most of the cases. None of the associations were found to be statistically significant. Table 4 elaborates the toxicities experienced by both the study groups during the 2nd follow up session.

Table 5: Comparing the Toxicities during the 3rd Follow Up in Both the Groups (n=66)

Toxicities	Arm A (n=33) [n/%]	Arm B (n=33) [n/%]	p-value
Diarrhea			
Grade 0	33 (100.0)	33 (100.0)	1.00
Grade I	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	

Proctitis			
Grade 0	32 (97.0)	33 (100.0)	1.00
Grade 1	1 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	
Bladder toxicity			
Dysuria			
Grade 0	32 (97.0)	33 (100.0)	1.00
Grade I	1 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	
Increased urinary frequency			
Grade 0	32 (97.0)	33 (100.0)	1.00
Grade I	1 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	
Vaginal toxicity			
Vaginal dryness			
Grade 0	30 (90.9)	29 (87.9)	1.00
Grade I	3 (9.1)	4 (12.1)	
Skin toxicity			
Grade 0	31 (93.9)	31 (93.9)	1.00
Grade I	2 (6.1)	2 (6.1)	

Note: *p-value estimated by Fisher’s Exact Test.

It is clearly evident that, at the 3rd follow up session, none of the participants complained diarrhea. Besides, only 1 patient from Arm A reported Grade 1 proctitis, dysuria and increased frequency of micturition. In addition, majority of the participants did not report any vaginal dryness (90.9% vs. 87.9%) or any skin toxicity (93.9% vs. 93.9%). None of the associations were found to be statistically significant. Table 5 illustrates the various toxicities experienced by the study sample during the 3rd follow up session.

Discussion

Present study was conducted to compare the toxicity outcomes of two brachytherapy regimens for patients with locally advanced carcinoma of the cervix who had received concurrent chemoradiotherapy (CCRT). The study consisted of 66 patients who were divided into two arms: Arm A (18 Gy in 2 fractions) and Arm B (21 Gy in 3 fractions).

In both Arm A and B, majority were aged between 30 to 50 years (66.7% vs 69.6%). Previous study done by Shirin et al. suggested that women of increasing age specially 40-50 years (41.18%), were found to be at increased risk of cervical cancer [10].

No significant differences were found between the arms concerning occupation or socio-economic status. The predominance of housewives (72.7% vs 78.8%) in both the groups throw light on the socioeconomic and educational disparities in cervical cancer patients in low-resource settings such as Bangladesh.

Comparing the toxicities between Arm A and Arm B during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd follow up sessions revealed no significant differences among the two groups. In the 1st follow up similar rates of diarrhea, proctitis, bladder toxicities namely dysuria and increased urinary frequency, vaginal toxicities namely vaginitis and vaginal dryness and skin toxicities were observed

between the arms. At the 2nd follow up session, both arms exhibited comparable toxicity profiles, with only minor differences in the incidence of Grade I and II toxicities, but no significant p-values (p>0.05) were detected. By the 3rd follow up session, both arms expressed minimal toxicity, with no cases of diarrhea or proctitis in Arm A; only a small incidence of proctitis in Arm A. Dysuria and increased frequency of micturition were similarly observed at Grade I in both arms. Dysuria & proctitis were more profound in arm A but without any significant p-value (p>0.05). The findings suggest that both treatment regimens have a comparable toxicity profile over time, with no significant adverse effects noted between the two arms. These findings are consistent with the study conducted by Meena et al., in which Arm A reported 14 patients with Grade I rectal toxicity, 24 with Grade II, and 1 with Grade III. In Arm B, 17 patients experienced Grade I and 22 had Grade II rectal toxicity. Similarly, in terms of bladder toxicity, 13 patients in Arm A experienced Grade I, 25 had Grade II, and 1 developed Grade III toxicity. In Arm B, 16 patients had Grade I and 23 had Grade II bladder toxicities. These results suggest that both HDR brachytherapy regimens are viable options, particularly when patient safety and treatment time reduction are important considerations [11]. Although Grade I toxicities were slightly more frequent in Arm A, the difference between the two groups was not statistically significant (p>0.05).

Additionally, Patel and colleagues demonstrated that delivering two fractions of HDR intracavitary brachytherapy at 9 Gy per fraction was both safe and effective, with minimal toxicity reported [7]. Similarly, Ghosh et al. supported the efficacy of a 9 Gy x 2 fractionation schedule, reporting acceptable profiles and validating its use in the treatment of cervical cancer [12].

The biggest limitation would be that, the follow up period was limited to six months, as a result of which late toxicities could not be identified.

Conclusion

Brachytherapy plays a pivotal role in the management of locally advanced cervical cancer (LACC). Various dose and fractionation schedules are currently practiced across different institutions, tailored to patient needs and institutional protocols. In the current study, both treatment regimens demonstrated comparable acute toxicity profiles, aligning with existing literature that suggest fraction size does not significantly impact either acute or late toxicity outcomes.

Given the high patient volume and limited healthcare resources in settings like Bangladesh, the HDR brachytherapy schedule of 18 Gy in 2 fractions emerges as a more practical and efficient option. With similar toxicity outcomes, shorter treatment duration, and improved patient compliance, this regimen may help

reduce hospital burden and optimize resource utilization in low-resource environments

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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